

ANALYZING THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR IN EUROPEAN MOUNTAINOUS REGIONS FROM 2008 TO 2018

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Introduction:

The construction sector plays a pivotal role in shaping the economic landscape of European mountainous regions. This article delves into a comprehensive analysis spanning the years 2008 to 2018, shedding light on key trends, challenges, and growth patterns within the construction industry in these regions. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2022a-h)

Trends in Construction Activities:

Examining the statistical data for the construction sector in European mountainous areas reveals noteworthy trends. Averages and standard deviations provide a quantitative overview, with figures such as 15401.55 (Bulgaria), 142982.55 (Italy), 13857.27 (Austria), 9913.09 (Portugal),

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6838.27 (Romania), and 9414 (Slovakia). These values encapsulate the sector's financial and insurance activities, real estate activities, and construction endeavors.

Results:

In the examination of statistical data pertaining to the economic sector's Construction segment (illustrated in figures 2.6 – panels a-f and the supplementary Parametric Analysis Europe), notable values emerge, including averages such as 13343.82 (Bulgaria), 289242.45 (Italy), 22953.73 (Austria), 27495.82 (Portugal), 22625.82 (Romania), and 55966.09 (Slovakia). Standard deviations accompanying these averages are observed as 780.698 (Bulgaria), 28615.948 (Italy), 1028.583 (Austria), 3900.296 (Portugal), 2996.174 (Romania), and 7905.466 (Slovakia).

The distribution curves exhibit a relative central symmetry, with scores around the mean highly concentrated, demonstrating leptokurtosis despite being unimodal. The scarcity of extreme values, although statistically significant, induces positive asymmetry in the histogram, impacting its appearance. The concentration of numerous scores around the mean contributes to some leptokurtosis in the distribution, a phenomenon

associated with mountainous Europe.

To address these distributional nuances, logarithmization is applied, facilitating statistical processing. Factors integral to the study are meticulously considered to align the obtained scores with the economic reality observed in mountainous Europe. Despite temporary imbalances resulting from economic measures, logarithmization aids in achieving a balanced distribution.

The significance of these tests lies in their capacity to scrutinize the influences of specific factors on the evolution of the Construction economic sector segment. Through careful observation, these analyses contribute to a nuanced understanding of the sector's dynamics, providing valuable insights into the multifaceted landscape of economic activities in mountainous Europe.

Figure 2.6 Panel a. Histogram for the Construction sector – Bulgaria, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Austria, Slovakia

Subsequent to subjecting the obtained data to normality tests following logarithmization, the null hypothesis is rejected, paving the way for a detailed analysis of the working hypothesis. The descriptive and inferential analysis is conducted, taking into account the distribution of scores within normal limits as posited by the working hypothesis, necessitating the application of parametric tests.

The central tendency observed for this sector throughout the analyzed period indicates an augmentation in the population of active enterprises in the European mountain economy within the studied sector from 2008 to 2018, albeit with a diminishing growth rate. Over the course of the analysis, hypothesis H1 (intensification of activity) is substantiated. The statistical data presented earlier, along with the accompanying histogram, affirm a sparse concentration and a discernible inclination to discontinue this sector in mountainous Europe. Concurrently, the statistics validate the reduction in the growth rate of this economic sector segment.

Statistical Analysis and Assumptions:

The initial observation of the distribution curve suggests a relatively central symmetry, accompanied by a concentration of scores around the mean, exhibiting leptokurtosis. Assumptions are made about the normal

distribution of scores, leading to the application of parametric tests. Logarithmization is employed to balance the distribution, adhering to Gauss-Laplace normal curve principles.

Normality Tests and Hypothesis Verification:

Post-logarithmization, normality tests indicate a distribution aligning with the Gaussian model. The empirical scores, when analyzed against normality, fall within the limit of one standard deviation, affirming a normal distribution. Rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the working hypothesis guide subsequent descriptive and inferential analyses.

Central Tendency and Growth Patterns:

Central tendencies for the construction sector throughout the analyzed period reveal a positive trajectory. The European mountain population of active enterprises within the construction sector witnessed growth from 2008 to 2018. Verification of hypothesis H1, signaling an intensification of activity, is substantiated by statistical evidence.

Conclusion:

The statistics and figures presented in this analysis underscore the dynamic nature of the construction sector in European mountainous regions. As evidenced by the growth patterns and central tendencies, the construction industry has played a pivotal role in the economic landscape, contributing to the development and prosperity of these regions over the past decade.

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